

PERCEPTIONS OF THE "LANGUAGE" CONCEPT OF TURKISH TEACHER CANDIDATES: A SAMPLE ANALYSIS OF METAPHORS

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Abstract:

In this study, it is aimed to determine the opinions of Turkish teacher candidates on the concept of "language". The study group of the study; in the academic year of 2018-2019, a total of 190 teacher candidates studying at Firat University Turkish Language Teaching Department are formed. In the study designed with qualitative research design, open-ended question form was used as data collection tool. The Turkish teacher candidates were asked to complete the expression using the metaphors "It looks like / language ... because ..." The obtained data were analyzed by the content analysis method and 167 valid metaphors were obtained for the concept of "language". Metaphores were collected under eight conceptual category and analyzed. As a result of the research, it was determined that prospective teachers developed many language metaphors. "Mirror (6.58%)", "bridge (5.38%)", "infant (5.38%)", "water (4.19%)", "sun (4.19%)", "tree (3.59%)" metaphors have been identified.

Keywords: language, Turkish teacher candidate, metaphor

1. Introduction

Language is a live communication tool which is contained within multiple functions. As Aksan (2003, p. 11) stated, language allows people to express their feelings and thoughts. Overall, language with a comprehensive definition; a natural means of communication between people, a "living being" which lives in its own rules and evolving; a social institution that brings and protects the nation; a unique structure consisting of sounds; it is the secret treaties system which is laid the foundation at unknown times (Ergin, 1987, p.7). The fact that the language is a structure consisting of sound and meaning units is related to the double articulation of the language.

Language includes concepts, concept space, interpretation of the concept, designs, feeling value within the scope of meaning (Karadüz, 2013, p. 292). The existence of concepts in the external world-becomes understandable with the richness

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of the language world of the individual. As it is known, people's concept world is mixed and intertwined. The concepts do not take place in the individual's mind in an isolated form. In order to determine teacher / student perceptions related to different concepts, there are studies about metaphor analysis in the body of literature (Tortop, 2013; Gveli, İpek & Atasoy, 2011; Ds, 2010; ztrk, 2007; Cerit, 2006; Ocak & Gndz, 2006; Saban, 2004, 2008, 2009; Guerrero & Villamil, 2002; Martinez, Sauleda & Huber).

Lakoff & Johnson (2005, p.27), who stated that most of the conceptual relationships in individuals possess are related to metaphors, define the metaphor as a concept or phenomenon to understand and explain the phenomenon through another concept or phenomenon. Metaphor is the use of a language that has occurred in certain rules of meaning formation and is not included in the dictionary before. In the contemporary metaphor theory developed by Lakoff & Johnson, there are two concepts in which one is understood through the other. While conceptual metaphors are related to the way individuals perceive the outside world, linguistic metaphors are the means of transferring abstract ideas to life (Akehirli, 2007, p.1).

Metaphors are used to redefine and review existing situations (Goldstein, 2005). In this way, it is easier to look the events from different angles by shedding light on current events and facts (Levine, 2012, p.172). Same time, metaphors, which are effective in determining the perceptions of individuals about a concept, are important in terms of expanding their ways of thinking and knowing how knowledge is formed (Arnett, 1999; Morgan, 2011, p. 464). Furthermore, Senemođlu (2005, p. 64) states that metaphors establish a link between the new knowledge and old knowledge acquired by the individual and thus facilitate the concrete expression of new knowledge. Metaphors, on the one hand, help organize the thinking and help the perception of the world (Guerrero & Villamil, 2002, p.96). At this point, Lakoff likens metaphors to brain maps. Metaphors help people organize their experiences. The brain produces images and links through concepts. Metaphors are also these link maps (Singh, 2010, p.128). While the image presents only a certain image to the opposite side, the metaphor conveys a mental frame about a phenomenon or event (Shuell, 1990 Act. Saban, 2008, p.460).

In recent years, metaphor analysis has been used as an intuitive tool to create awareness about theoretical assumptions and to be used in educational environments (Arslan & Bayrakçı, 2006; Guerrero & Villamil, 2002, p.97). Determining the interests, attitudes and wishes of prospective teachers is one of the main objectives of teacher education, but also important in contributing to their professional development (Noyes, 2004, p. 245).The use of metaphor and metaphoric elements in education and training also reveal the perceptions of students by increasing teachers' functionality in the school (Bne-Peretz, Mendelson & Kron, 2003).

Considering the studies on the subject related to the body of literature, Bozik (2002) conducted a metaphorical study to determine the perceptions of the university students. As a result of the research, students produced 35 valid metaphors. Bozik (2002) examines metaphors by categorizing them and as a result of the research; he has gained positive and negative metaphors about student concept. Tortop (2013)

determined the perceptions of prospective teachers about the university lecturers'. In the research, prospective teachers produced 183 different metaphors about the university lecturer. Among the metaphors divided into different categories, the university lecturer; is perceived as "source of information and guidance", "pathfinder", "changing-differing person", "minacious" and "an all-rounder". Gveli, İpek, Atasoy & Gveli (2011) examined the perceptions of the preservice teachers about the mathematics lesson. As a result of the data obtained from 200 pre-service teachers, it was determined that the students described mathematics lesson as; "an exciting course", "boring course", "course consisting of different topics."Ksteriođlu (2014) examined the perceptions of pre-service teachers about the concept of school administrator. The pre-service teachers produced close to 60 metaphors about the concept of school administrators.

As seen, metaphor analysis is a method used to reflect the perceptions of students about various concepts. In this way, especially the students' opinions about different concepts are examined in detail and clues about the deficiencies in the educational environment are obtained. In this research, it is aimed to determine the perceptions of students about the concept of language. The number of studies conducted on the concept of language in the body of literature review was quite limited. In this respect, it is foreseen that the research will contribute to the literature.

The aim of this research is to determine the perceptions of Turkish teacher candidates on the concept of language and compare the results. The following research questions have been determined for this general purpose.

- 1) What are the metaphors used by Turkish teacher candidates in terms of language?
- 2) In which categories can the metaphors be collected in terms of their common characteristics?

2. Method

This topic includes information about the research design, participants, data collection tool and data analysis.

1.1. Research Design

The research is designed with phenomenology from qualitative research approaches. Phenomenology is related to cases that we are aware of but do not have a detailed knowledge. We encounter in different ways in daily life with these phenomena, however, this does not mean that the phenomenon is fully defined. Studies aim to investigate the facts that are not completely foreign or clearly understood by the individual, constitute a suitable research base for phenomenology. (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013, p.78).

Effective, emotional and intensive human experiences are studied in Phenemonological approaches (Merriam, 2018, p. 26). In this study, the perceptions of prospective teachers about the concept of language were tried to be determined.

1.2. Participants

The research was carried out with the first, second, third and fourth year students of Turkish Faculty of Education, Department of Turkish Language Teaching and Social Sciences Teaching Program in the spring semester of 2018-2019 academic year. Total of 190 students participated in the study, 49 (25.78%) of first grade, 48 (25.26%) from second grade, 53 (27.89%) from third grade and 40 (21.05%) from fourth grade. The distribution of participants according to their gender is given in the table below:

Table1: Distribution of Students in the Study Group by Gender

Gender	<i>f</i>	%
Woman	120	63.16
Man	70	36.84
Total	190	100

1.3. Data collection tool

During preparation of the data collection tool, studies are examined on the subject in the body of literature (Alger, 2009; Cerit, 2008; ztrk, 2007; Saban, 2004) and data collection tools were created. In this research from related literature movement, were asked to complete using metaphor from the Turkish teacher candidates of the "Language is similar, because....." expression. The metaphors of the pre-service teachers' language concept and the reasons for choosing this metaphor are intended to have a logical basis with this expression.

At the stage of data collection, pre-service teachers were informed about the purpose of the research and method of application. In addition, brief information about metaphors was given in order to activate the thoughts of teachers and concentrate on the study. They were asked from the students to explain the cause of a metaphor for explain the concept of language. The application before the students' graduate course has been implemented within the knowledge of the responsible course instructor. During the application, the relevant forms distributed to teachers, were asked to concentrate to form for 15 minutes and then the forms are collected.

1.4. Data Analysis

The forms belonging to Turkish teacher candidates were coded by the researcher and then the data was transferred to the computer environment. In the analysis of the data, at the body of literature, the path followed in the studies on the subject (Saban, 2009; Gven & Gven, 2009) was followed:

1. Detection, separation and coding of metaphors;
2. Creating of the main metaphors;
3. Category creation phase;
4. Providing validity and reliability.

First, metaphors were determined in the research, then metaphors were divided into groups within themselves.

1.4.1 Detection and coding of metaphors

First, the forms were coded in a sequential manner and each student's form was determined (1, 10,  20 etc). Then the metaphors produced by the teacher candidates about the language concept and listed as alphabetically. Here, it has been checked whether pre-service teachers express a metaphor clearly. Non-validated ones were removed. A metaphor, which was expressed by each preservice teacher, was coded and a list was formed. At this stage, metaphors produced as invalid and unjustified are winnowed. As a result of the study, it was determined that the students developed 167 valid metaphors.

1.4.2 Creating of main metaphors

The metaphors produced by preservice teachers, are divided into different conceptual categories. After determined 167 metaphors which are similar as nature, are grouped under the same title. At this stage, the researcher transferred the metaphors expressed in the structure of the long sentence, preserving the language and words of the preservice teachers. The metaphors representing the group in the clearest way were transferred to the list.

1.4.3 Category creation stage

Metaphors developed by the preservice teachers during the category formation phase were analyzed in detail in terms of the common characteristics. It is examined how pre-service teachers express their views on the concept of language. As a result of the study, metaphors developed by the candidates are divided into eight different conceptual categories. In the later stages of the research, metaphors were examined in detail.

1.4.4 Providing validity and reliability

A number of strategies have been used to increase the validity and reliability of the research. Considering the importance of related issues, it is seen that the credibility, transferability and coder reliability are important in qualitative studies in the body of literature (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013, p. 298).

In order to increase the credibility of the research, missing and inaccurate ones from the feedback given by the pre-service teachers were eliminated. Again, were asked from the teacher candidates to check their feedback and in this way participant confirmation is provided. A detailed description of the metaphors has been made in the manner in which the pre-service teachers' raw data are separated according to the concepts and themes.

The data of the research were analyzed in detail and thus the transferability of the research was ensured. Data were analyzed by content analysis and phenomenon components were coded by the researcher. In order to ensure coder reliability, a field expert other than the investigator re-encoded the data. In terms of coder reliability, the formula was developed by Miles & Huberman (2016, p. 64) between the two encodings (Reliability = Number of Consensus / Total Consensus + Number of dissensus) * 100. As a result of process reliability is calculated as 88%.

2. Findings

In this section, the conceptual titles of the metaphors developed by the prospective teachers about the language concept and list of metaphors under these titles, will be included. The list of valid metaphors that teacher trainees have created regarding the concept of language is given in Table 2. It is seen that the participants have a total of 167 valid metaphors for the language concept. It is seen that teacher candidates express their language concept mostly with mirror (11), baby (9), bridge (9), human (8), sun (7), tree (6) metaphors. In addition, while prospective teachers reflected their perceptions about language, they developed metaphors such as stream, mother, car engine, atom, suitcase, brain, security, porter, butterfly, breath, art, time machine.

Table 2: Metaphors which are created by the prospective teachers regarding concept of language

Metaphor	f	%	Metaphor	f	%	Metaphor	f	%
Tree	6	3.59	Literature	1	0.005	Odor	1	0.005
Family	1	0.005	Bread	2	1.19	Bridge	9	5.38
Stream	4	2.39	Security	1	0.005	Culture	2	1.19
Mind	1	0.005	House	2	1.19	Assembly	1	0.005
Mother	1	0.005	Saint	1	0.005	Season	1	0.005
Agreement	1	0.005	Universe	2	1.19	Momentum law	1	0.005
Car engine	2	1.19	Sapling	2	1.19	Breath	3	1.79
Vehicle	4	2.39	Elephant	1	0.005	Ocean	2	1.19
Love	1	0.005	Skyscraper	1	0.005	Backbone	1	0.005
Atom	1	0.005	Sky	3	1.79	Liberty	1	0.005
Moon	1	0.005	Rose	2	1.19	Window	1	0.005
Shoe	1	0.005	Sun	7	4.19	Color	1	0.005
Mirror	11	6.58	Porter	1	0.005	Sprit	1	0.005
Suitcase	1	0.005	Life	2	1.19	Wind	2	1.19
Baby	9	5.38	Treasury	1	0.005	Clock	1	0.005
Brain	2	1.19	Light	3	1.79	Hair	1	0.005
Mobile phone	4	2.39	Pearl	1	0.005	Art	1	0.005
Core	1	0.005	Human	8	4.79	Love	1	0.005
Flower	1	0.005	Castle	1	0.005	Water	7	4.19
Cement	2	1.19	Pen	3	1.79	Basic	1	0.005
Shepherd	1	0.005	Character	1	0.005	Theater	1	0.005
Vein	1	0.005	Dark room	1	0.005	Soil	3	1.79
Sea	3	1.79	Butterfly	1	0.005	Road	1	0.005
Nature	3	1.79	Identity	2	1.19	Time machine	3	1.79
World	3	1.79	Book	4	2.39	Total	167	

The metaphors of the prospective teachers' opinions about the concept of language are categorized. Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage values of the categories. The metaphors developed by prospective teachers are divided into eight categories.

Table 3: Categories related to language concept

Categories	<i>f</i>	%
Transfer tool	39	23.3
A developing entity	34	20.3
Eternal entity	19	11.3
Value reflecting entity	19	11.3
Basic need	18	10.7
An illuminant entity	16	9.5
A valuable entity	14	8.3
Protective entity	8	4.7
Total	167	100

Referring to Table 3, it is seen that preservice teachers are perceived the language as; transfer tool (23.3%), a developing entity (20.3%), an eternal entity (11.3%), value reflecting entity (11.3%), basic need (10.7%), an illuminant entity (9.5%), valuable entity (8.3%) and protective entity (4.7%). Although prospective teachers mostly see language as a means of transmission but they also stated that it was a living and developing entity.

2.1 Language as a Transfer Tool

Teacher candidates under the metaphor have created 39 language category as a transfer tool. These metaphors are given in Table 4:

Table 4: Teachers' perceptions of language as a means of transfer

Metaphor name	<i>f</i>	%	Metaphor name	<i>f</i>	%
Stream	4	10.25	Elephant	1	2.56
Car engine	2	5.12	Porter	1	2.56
Vehicle	4	10.25	Pencil	3	7.69
Shoe	1	2.56	Bridge	9	23.07
Suitcase	1	2.56	Culture	2	5.12
Mobil phone	4	10.25	Assembly	1	2.56
Vein	1	2.56	Road	1	2.56
Saint	1	2.56	Time machine	3	7.69
Total 39					

As shown in Table 4, there are 39 metaphors under the language category as a means of transfer. Among these metaphors, it is seen that the metaphor of the bridge (23.07%) is frequently used by the teacher candidates. Again, mobile phone (10.25%), stream (10.25%), vehicle (10.25%), pencil (7.69%) and time machine (7.69%) metaphors were preferred by more than one teacher candidate. Other metaphors were used only by one teacher candidate.

In this category, some metaphors used by pre-service teachers and their opinions on the subject are listed below:

"Language allows people to express themselves. The language is similar to a bridge in terms of transferring the material and spiritual elements of a civilization to an advanced level and linking it with information." (186, bridge metaphor)

"The language has been flowing like a water for a long time and has reached the next generations with a lot of accumulation. If we evaluate its dynamicness, the language is non-stationary and picks up accumulation in the ways it passes. Language will always be like a stream until the end of humanity." (166, stream metaphor)

"Nowadays mobile phones are everywhere with us. Just like language." (189, mobile phone metaphor)

2.2 Language as a developing entity

Prospective teachers formed 34 metaphors under the language category as a developing entity. These metaphors are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Teachers' perceptions of language as a developing entity

Metaphor name	f	%	Metaphor name	f	%
Tree	6	17.64	Butterfly	1	2.94
Baby	9	26.47	Season	1	2.94
Flower	1	2.94	Momentum law	1	2.94
Nature	3	8.82	Clock	1	2.94
Sapling	2	5.88	Hair	1	2.94
Human	8	23.52			
			Total	34	

There are 34 metaphors under this category. 9 of these metaphors are associated with infants, 8 of them with human, 6 with trees, 3 with nature and 2 with sapling. Other metaphors were developed by a teacher candidate. 26.47% of prospective teachers established a relationship between language and baby as a developing entity. Some of the statements contained in this category are:

"Language, like a newborn baby, born, grows, develops, grows old, and then disappears. In other words, the language contains all the developmental characteristics of babies. (2, baby metaphor)"

"Language, like a tree, takes root in history and grows fruits. The tree is fertile entity in here. Language increases expression power through words. The tree just as how fertile with its fruits, human being, productively with language, put down roots as a tree. (176, tree metaphor)"

"How the human consists of cells, language also consists of letters, words and sentences. Human cells combine and form a wholeness and body. The elements of the language combine and reach a whole and enliven. (178, human metaphor)"

2.3 Language as an Eternal Entity

Teacher candidates have created 19 metaphors under the language category as an eternal entity. These metaphors are given in Table 6.

Table 6: Teachers' perceptions of language as an infinite entity

Metaphor name	f	%	Metaphor name	f	%
Agreement	1	5.26	Ocean	2	10.52
Sea	3	15.78	Liberty	1	5.26
World	3	15.78	Window	1	5.26
Universe	2	10.52	Sprit	1	5.26
Sky	3	15.78	Wind	2	10.52
			Total	19	

A total of 19 metaphors are included under this category. Some of these metaphors are related to the world (15.78%), creation of the universe (10.52%), sky (15.78%). Also, under this category, window, spirit and wind metaphors were included. In the following, the relationship between the preservice teachers' language and eternal entities and reasons are included;

"Language is same as a sea which each drop carries different meaning and essence. Even though it sometimes blur, is always pure and clean. ( 131, sea metaphor)"

"There are many nationalities in the world. Many planets in the universe. There are many dialects, accent and subdialects in the language. So language is similar to the world. Wide and endless. ( 49, the metaphor of the world)"

"It is not clear when and where the language begins and ends. Language is such an infinite entity in terms of its scope, power. It is always exist and as long as the life goes on, will continue to exist even sometimes shows a change. ( 143, the metaphor of the sky)"

2.4 Language as an entity which reflects the value

Teacher candidates created 19 metaphors under the language category as a value reflecting entity. These metaphors are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Preservice Teachers' Perceptions of language as a value-reflecting entity

Metaphor name	f	%	Metaphor name	f	%
Atom	1	5.26	Odor	1	5.26
Mirror	11	57.89	Color	1	5.26
Literature	1	5.26	Art	1	5.26
Identity	2	10.52	Theater	1	5.26
			Total	19	

As an entity that reflects value, it is seen that common emphasis was made through the mirror metaphor under the statement in the language category. It is observed that pre-service teachers often prefer mirror metaphor when you look at the Table 7. Giving coverage to the pre-service teachers' choice of metaphors and their reasons under this category on below;

"We reflect our thoughts, emotions to the other people through language. Mirror reflects the face of the human, also language reflect what is in the brain, heart, feelings and thoughts to the other people. How we evaluate ourselves with our reflections in the mirror, the person we tell our thoughts evaluates us with our language. (15, mirror metaphor)"

"The most basic being that makes us human, is language. A person who has lost his language, lost all his identity. We find identity with our language. (.80, identity metaphor)"

"How theater is a means of explaining values, events, people, thoughts from within life, language is also as like that. (O 140, theater metaphor)"

2.5. Language, as a basic need

Participants formed 18 metaphors under the language category as the basic need. These metaphors are given in Table 8.

Table 8: Preservice Teachers' perceptions of language as a basic need

Metaphor name	f	%	Metaphor name	f	%
Mind	1	5.55	Breath	3	16.66
Bread	2	11.11	Water	7	38.88
Life	2	11.11	Soil	3	16.66
			Total	18	

There are 18 metaphors in total under this category. 7 of these metaphors are water, 3 are breath, 3 are earth, 2 are life, 2 are bread and 1 is mind. Teacher candidates got in contact between language and basic needs of people. Teacher candidates' explanation of the reasons that why they chose that metaphor, are listed below:

"How water is the basic necessity to live, the language is also as same for us. If we want to maintain our lives in a good way, we need to establish a healthy communication with other people. Language is a need for this. How much is a healthy life in a world where people cannot express their feelings, thoughts and needs? (O125, metaphor of water)"

"Language may vary according to time and society. Soil becomes fertile or barren according to the labor of the farmer. The words, literary products, beings that we plant in

the language soil, grow and multiply. We fulfill our needs to live with these products (Ö117, metaphor of soil)".

"The language is holy as bread, essential, valuable, need. (Ö151, bread metaphor)"

2.6. Language as an illuminating entity

Teacher candidates formed 16 metaphors under the language category as an illuminating entity. These metaphors are presented in Table 9:

Table 9: Preservice Teachers' perceptions of language as an illuminating entity

Metaphor name	f	%
Book	4	25
Sun	7	43.75
Light	3	18.75
Moon	1	6.25
Dark room	1	6.25
Total	16	100

As seen in Table 9, there are 16 metaphors in the language category as an illuminating entity. While teacher candidates explaining the concept of language, it is seen that the metaphor of the sun comes to the fore under this category. Again, books (25%), light (18.75%), month (6.25%) and dark room (6.25%) are among the metaphors under this heading.

Teacher candidates' explanations about the metaphors are located on below;

"How the sun illuminates our world, language illuminates a society. The societies that cannot use their language, cannot develop, always remain in the dark. How the sun illuminates and warms our world, the language becomes the light of the dark minds. (Ö161, sun metaphor)"

"Just as a book opens and new knowledges comes out, the language as well. We have more knowledges to express our opinion when we grasp of the language. This knowledges make us feel strong and enlighten our way. (Ö12, book metaphor)"

"Language is a light to those left in the dark. Words and sounds in the language clarify our thoughts which remained in dark. Bright to light them. (O24, light metaphor)"

2.7. Language as a valuable entity

Prospective teachers formed 11 metaphors belonging to the language category as a valuable entity. These metaphors are shown in Table 10:

Table 10: Pre-service teachers' perceptions of language as a valuable entity

Metaphor name	f	%	Metaphor name	f	%
Love	1	9.09	Rose	2	18.18

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Brain	2	18.18	Treasure	1	9.09
Core	1	9.09	Pearl	1	9.09
Cement	2	18.18	Like	1	9.09
Security	1	9.09	Basic	1	9.09
Skyscraper	1	9.09			
			Total	14	

Prospective teachers, love (9.09%), brain (18.18%), core (9.09%), cement (18.18%), security (9.09%), skyscraper (9.09%), rose (9.09%) 18.18%), treasury (9.09%), pearl (9.09%), basic (9.09%) and like (9.09%) metaphors were formed as a valuable entity, under the language category. Explanation why teacher candidates establish relationships between assets and language, choose these metaphors, are listed on below;

“Rose is a very beautiful flower, but it changes when dried and begins to fade. Finally, the dried leaves remain. The language is similar to rose with this unique feature. It is as beautiful and special as it is. Some words in the language are sometimes not used and forgotten by people. Here are those words that are forgotten, dried leaves of roses. (119 rose metaphor)”

“Language is an entity with a high level structure, such as the human brain. The brain, which is necessary for people to survive, has complex and not interpret points. (108, brain metaphor)”

“How the person you loved, is so important and valuable to you, language is like that for the society. No happiness without love, so the nations without language. (141, metaphor of love)”

2.8. Language as a protective entity

Participants formed 8 metaphors under the language category as a protective entity. These metaphors are given in Table 11.

Table 11: Teacher candidates' perceptions of language as a protective entity

Metaphor name	f	%	Metaphor name	f	%
Family	1	14.28	Castle	1	14.28
Mother	1	14.28	Character	1	14.28
Shepherd	1	14.28	Backbone	1	14.28
House	2	28.57			
			Total	8	

It is observed that pre-service teachers constitute family, mother, shepherd, house, castle, character and backbone metaphors under the language category as a protective entity when referred to the Table 11. The explanations of the pre-service teachers about the metaphors they selected are given below;

"The house is a shelter that protects people from cold, heat, evil and strangers, so the language is same.... Human is in comfortable mood when he-she has been using his-her language as she-he is in home. She-he takes care of his-her language as she-he takes care of his-her home. She-he protects it, purifies from foreign words and takes refuge to the language in his difficult times." (41 house metaphor)

"Our mother is the only being who always protects us from evil in this life. Language is as like the mother of nations. It carries the existence of nations from the past to the future." (123, mother metaphor)

"Our backbone keeps us alive and protects our internal organs against external influences. Just like a backbone, the language keeps communities alive and prevents them from disintegrating. Their survival depends on to protect their language." (30, backbone metaphor)

3. Discussion, Conclusion and Suggestions

In the literature, there are many studies conducted to determine the perceptions of prospective teachers on different concepts. (Guerrero & Villamil 2002; Saban & Kobeker, 2005; Shaw & Mahlios, 2008). Metaphors are used to determine students' perceptions of a particular subject and obtain information regarding learning and teaching environment. As stated Tobin & Lamaster (1992), it is used to make the teaching environment more effective, to determine the activities to be applied in the course, choose effective teaching methods. At this point, it can be said that metaphors are effective on developing teaching activities and determining the students' education and perceptions.

In this study, which was conducted to determine the perceptions of Turkish pre-service teachers about the concept of language, pre-service teachers developed a large number of metaphors with different characteristics. These metaphors used by prospective teachers reflect the positive viewpoints of the candidates against the language. According to the findings of the study, the metaphors developed by teacher candidates are discussed under eight conceptual titles. Information on the conceptual categories developed by the 190 teacher candidates about the language concept, are as follows: 23% of metaphors attracted notice that language is a transfer tool, 20% is a constantly developing and changing entity, 11% is an infinite entity with no boundaries, 10% is the basic need, 9% is an illuminating entity, 8% is a valuable entity, and % 4 is a protective entity.

In fact, it can be said that it is not possible to express a concept only through a metaphor. As Yob dwells on (2003), metaphors, not the case itself or event but it is symbolized state. That's why the metaphor is different from the one it points and provides a deep and meaningful view of the phenomenon in question.

Most of the participants stated that they perceived language as a means of transfer tool (23%) and a developing entity (20%). Under these conceptual categories, as

a means of transfer, bridge, stream, vehicle, mobile phone, porter, suitcase, vessel, culture, assembly, saint, road, time machine, shoe, and car engine metaphors are located. Prospective teachers stated that they perceived the language as a means of transferring the emotions, thoughts, spiritual values, customs and traditions from generation to generation. This finding of the research, is similar to Balta (2015) and Sevim, Veyis & Kınay's (2012) studies. Balta (2015), in his study, stated that the language of the pre-service teachers is a carrier duty of the elements between the societies' past and future. Sevim, Veyis & Kınay (2012) concluded that prospective teachers perceived Turkish as a means of storing and transmitting cultural values.

Prospective teachers also stated that they look upon the language as a developing, maturing and dying entity. They expressed their perceptions of language as a developing entity with metaphors such as tree, baby, flower, sapling, butterfly, season and hair. Especially the tree and tree root to grow, develop and take root in the place, was preferred by the participants in the transfer of perceptions about the language. This finding of the study is similar to the research results of Pilav & Elakıtmıř (2013). Pilav & Elakıtmıř (2013) stated that water and tree metaphors are frequently preferred by prospective teachers in their studies aimed to determine the perceptions about Turkish concept. Again in Sevim, Veyis & Kınay stated that water and tree metaphors are among the most used metaphors by the participants.

11% of metaphors were examined under the language category as an infinite entity. The participants stated that the metaphors of the sea, world, sky, the universe, ocean, liberty, window, spirit, wind, and beginning and end points of the language are unclear. Participants have established a relationship between these metaphors, eternity of entities and universe. Under the language title as a value-reflecting entity, metaphors such as atom, mirror, odor, color, art, identity were included.

Participants stated that they perceive the language as an entity that reflects the material and spiritual values of societies, and that it is necessary to study the language of a nation and its language in order to understand its identity. Some of the participants expressed the basic need metaphors for the continuation of life. Participants indicated that language is a necessary fact for the continuation of a nation and are established a relationship between language, mind, bread, life, breath, water, soil metaphors. Candidates stated that language is a mind, brain of the nation and it is not possible for the nations to live without language.

In the language category as an illuminating entity, it was seen that the book, sun, light, moon and dark room metaphors were used by the participants. Especially the metaphor of the sun came to forefront in this category. The finding of this study shows similarity of Balta's study (2015) finding. Balta stated in his study (2015), pre-service teachers say that their mother tongue sheds light on personality, emotions and thoughts like a sun. It is possible to say that the number of metaphors created under this category is less than other categories. In the language category as a valuable asset, the participants established a relationship between language and concepts of love, trust, rose, pearl, like and treasure. Family, mother, house, shepherd, castle, character, backbone metaphors are discussed in the language category as a protective entity.

Mother metaphor also came to the fore in Pilav & Elakıtımsı studies (2013). Mother metaphor, which gives direction to our lives and is included in the category of cultural transfer tool, is the most frequently used metaphor in this category by the candidates.

As a result, metaphors can be used to expose and explain the mental images that teacher candidates have for the language concept. When the metaphors used by the students are examined, it is concluded that the students are aware of the power, boundaries, importance and qualities of language. However, in some of the participants' forms, the reasons were not fully expressed and scattered expressions stand out. During the practice, some students had difficulty in expressing their thoughts through metaphors. Bayat & etinkaya (2016) encountered similar problems in their studies. Most of the teacher candidates had difficulty in producing clues. Based on these problems, figurative and language-enhancing activities can be done in Turkish language studies and Turkish lessons. Again, in Turkish language teaching programs, gains can be given to develop imaginary thinking. In this way, it can be aimed to educate individuals whose mother tongue and skills are improved by enabling students to use their language skills more effectively.

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A SAMPLE ANALYSIS OF METAPHORS

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